

DIRECTIONS OF DEVELOPMENT OF BUSINESS ACTIVITY IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES

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Abstract: This article discusses the economic mechanism of business development in industrial enterprises and its necessity, the models used in the planning of modern strategies. Measures aimed at the development of the industrial sector are described in terms of increasing the economic efficiency of enterprises, concepts related to the development and organization of entrepreneurship in the industrial sector, and factors determining the development of small businesses and private entrepreneurship.

Keywords: industry, planning, small business, mechanism, economic efficiency, modern strategy, market, entrepreneurship, cost.

Introduction

The industrial sector, considered one of the leading sectors, is one of the sectors that has been making a great contribution to the development of our country's economy. Taking into account the wide range of opportunities for further development of this industrial network, increasing the efficiency of the network, producing competitive products suitable for international markets, and introducing the industrial brand to the whole world are urgent issues. All the measures aimed at the development of the industrial network serve to increase the economic efficiency of enterprises and the production of competitive products. More effective organization of business activities of industrial enterprises, determining the level of competitiveness in the domestic and foreign markets, studying the level of effectiveness of competitiveness factors, giving a proper

assessment to enterprises, identifying shortcomings and problems, and effectively using the experiences of developed countries are of urgent importance.

In this regard, in the words of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoev, “as a result of systemic changes in the economy, the share of industry in the structure of the gross domestic product is expected to increase from 35 percent to 37 percent this year”. However, in some cities and districts, this very important issue is not given enough attention. As a result, the share of industry in 27 districts of the republic does not even reach 1% of the regional indicator. Therefore, it is necessary to develop medium and long-term programs for the development of each district and city industry [1]. Industry is one of the main sectors of the economy of our republic. Because the industry is fundamentally different from other sectors and sectors with its added value creation, its role in meeting the needs of the population and its high-level production locomotive. The development of the industrial network leads to the development of the national economy at a steady pace.

Analysis of literature on the topic

The mechanism of development of business activity in the industrial sector is a set of methods, methods and principles of organizing business activities of enterprises belonging to the industrial sector. In general, many well-known economists, including L.I.Abalkin, N.Q. Yoldoshev, Sh.N. Zaynutdinov, G.M. Qasimov, E.Kh.Makhmudov, and others, gave their opinions on economic mechanisms and development mechanisms. [2]. V.F. Phillipov states that the economic mechanism includes planning, economic supports and incentives, organizational structures, methods and methods, various forms of participation of the labor team in the development of production, which are the main elements of development [3].

So, economic mechanism and development mechanism interact, they are very close concepts. It should also be noted that in many economic literature, the

concepts of "development mechanism" and "economic mechanism" and "economic mechanism" are not seriously differentiated from each other. However, in the conditions of the market economy, the concept of "Development mechanism" is the main organizational economic category and includes other mechanisms related to business activity.

Analysis and results

Thus, the development mechanism should be viewed as an active element of the development system that provides influence on the factors on which the results of the activity of the development object depend. Therefore, the development mechanism is a set of methods, tools and levers that affect development processes used by development entities to achieve development goals. A development mechanism is a set of influence tools used in development or a set of tools used in development.

The mechanism of development is a set of motivations for the active activity of personnel, which determines both the possibility of development and the effectiveness. However, the given definitions do not indicate the subject of implementation of the sum of elements of development influence. Therefore, the development mechanism of a small enterprise is a set of principles, methods, functions and instruments of the development influence applied by them to ensure the flexibility of the leaders on the process of economic and social activity of the enterprise.

Fig.1. Factors determining the need to develop small business and private entrepreneurship

Accordingly, improvement and research of the mechanism of development of small business and private entrepreneurship in industrial enterprises is one of the urgent issues of today. It should be recognized that the possibility of conducting business activities in industrial enterprises is directly related to their production potential.[4] Since "Industrial production potential" is a complex concept as an economic category, its constituents also consist of many elements. In particular, in the studies of A. O. Larionov and other economists, industrial potential is characterized by indicators of material technical, financial, labor, infrastructural and investment potential.[5] These indicators determine the level of development of the industrial enterprise's production potential through innovative elements.

The potential of an industrial enterprise indicates the level of the country's ability and capacity to produce raw materials and all available resources. Today, the industry provides an opportunity to effectively solve problems such as ensuring the necessary balance in the market, increasing the competitiveness of

the economy and the income of the population, localization of production, and this industry plays an important role in creating new jobs. In particular, the creation of one job in the manufacturing industry leads to the creation of two or three jobs in other industries.[6]

It is possible to carry out business activities in industrial enterprises and reach the level of sustainable development at the expense of management and regulatory mechanisms. One of the strategic directions of creating conditions for the development of business activities in industrial enterprises is the creation of a favorable macroeconomic environment, which includes such tools as the budget, tax, monetary credit, price and currency policy.

L.I. Abalkin says that the economic mechanism is a set of forms and methods of operation, includes not only basic but also superstructural elements that influence each other [7]. V.A. According to Ulyanov, the economic mechanism is a system that forms production relations as a method of organizing production, a form of economic management (plan, economic regulations, price, profit, wages, finance, credit, decision-making), and it is not only production in relations, it means organization of production forces and structure.[8]

E.E. Vershigora states that the economic mechanism results from the joint action and harmony of planning, economic incentives, market mechanism and organizational structure.[9]

Taking into account the above, we can say that the economic mechanism is more specific to the macro level. In our opinion, the development mechanism consists of 5 main elements:

- development object and subject;
- goals and functions;
- development bodies and organizational structure;
- methods and principles;
- means.

In our opinion, development system and development mechanism are not the same. The difference is that the mechanism includes development methods, forms and functions. In addition to the above, the system also includes a development apparatus that performs development functions.

Conclusions and suggestions

In scientific sources, the country's economic development and its stable growth are determined mainly by the level of development of the industrial sector in its economy. The theoretical foundations of the development of entrepreneurship in industrial enterprises have been put forward by economists who have conducted research on economics, marketing and management in their scientific works and have shown that its development directly leads to the solution of a number of economic problems in the national economy. Effective conduct of business activity in industrial enterprises and its sustainable development depends primarily on the way in which it is organized and managed.

The world's leading brand companies show that the effective performance of work often depends on how and in what form it is organized. Therefore, it will be difficult for industrial enterprises to develop their business activities in accordance with the market demand without introducing its organizational and economic mechanisms. The industrial sector, which is one of the leading branches of the national economy, and the realization of entrepreneurship in the enterprises operating in them depends on many factors. A number of economists first of all point out internal and external factors and other factors.

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